

Research Article

VocaDual for Kids (Enhancing English Vocabulary for Malay-Speaking Kindergarten Children)

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Abstract: VocaDual is an innovative educational tool developed to enhance bilingual vocabulary acquisition among young learners, specifically targeting preschool children in Malaysia. This interactive game employs a combination of hidden animals, jumble words, and crossword puzzle games to engage students in a dual-language learning environment, incorporating both Malay and English vocabulary. By addressing common language learning challenges such as limited exposure to English and a lack of engaging resources, VocaDual provides a dynamic approach to language education. The game is designed to be customizable, catering to diverse learning needs and preferences, which promotes active engagement and better retention of vocabulary. VocaDual's design is informed by research highlighting the importance of bilingual education in multilingual societies like Malaysia, where children often face difficulties in acquiring proficiency in a second language. Preliminary qualitative studies, including feedback from teachers and learners at Tabika Perpaduan Daerah Batu Pahat Johor Darul Takzim, demonstrate the game's effectiveness in improving vocabulary retention and motivating young learners. This tool not only enhances language skills but also encourages creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. VocaDual has the potential for broader application across multilingual educational contexts, offering a novel solution to support language development in early childhood education.

Keywords: bilingual vocabulary acquisition, interactive educational tool, language learning challenges, early childhood education, and multilingual educational contexts.

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1. INTRODUCTION

VocaDual is an innovative educational game designed to enhance bilingual vocabulary acquisition among young learners in Malaysia's multilingual preschool environment. In a country like Malaysia, where multiple languages are spoken, children often face challenges in learning both the national language, Malay, and English. VocaDual addresses these challenges by providing a dynamic and engaging learning experience through interactive elements like hidden animal games, jumble word activities, and crossword puzzles. These features aim to make language learning enjoyable and effective, thereby promoting better vocabulary retention and language skills.

The game leverages educational principles that highlight the benefits of early exposure to multiple languages, which can significantly enhance cognitive abilities and linguistic skills (Bialystok, 2017). Research also shows that interactive, game-based learning is particularly effective for young learners, as it engages multiple senses and provides context-driven understanding (Gee, 2007). VocaDual integrates these principles by combining playful activities with language instruction, allowing children to learn and practice vocabulary in both Malay and English simultaneously.

This dual-language approach addresses common barriers such as limited exposure to English and a lack of engaging resources, while also catering to individual learning needs.

Initial studies conducted in educational settings like Tabika Perpaduan Daerah Batu Pahat, Johor Darul Takzim, have shown promising results. The findings indicate that VocaDual significantly improves vocabulary acquisition and motivates students to actively participate in their language-learning journey. As bilingualism becomes increasingly important in a globalized world, tools like VocaDual provide an innovative way to equip young learners with essential language skills (Kang, 2019; García & Wei, 2014).

By utilizing engaging, interactive activities, VocaDual helps children build their bilingual vocabulary in an enjoyable and meaningful way. It not only enhances language skills but also fosters a love for learning, which can have a lasting impact on their educational journey.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The development of VocaDual, a bilingual vocabulary acquisition tool, involved a carefully planned process utilizing Figma software and Microsoft PowerPoint to create an engaging and interactive learning experience for young learners in Malaysia's multilingual preschool environment. These tools were specifically chosen for their complementary capabilities, which helped craft a game that is both effective in educational terms and captivating for preschool students.

2.1 Using Figma Software for Game Design

Figma software played a crucial role in designing the core components of the VocaDual game. This software is known for its versatile design capabilities, which were essential for creating the game's dynamic and interactive elements, such as hidden animal games, jumble word activities, and crossword puzzles. These features are particularly important for maintaining the attention and interest of preschool-aged children, who benefit from visually appealing and stimulating content. The use of Figma software enabled the developers to integrate rich animations, smooth transitions, and vibrant graphics, which are crucial in capturing young learners' imaginations and making the language-learning process enjoyable (Meyer & Land, 2003).

Additionally, Figma's advanced design tools facilitated the incorporation of auditory elements, such as sound effects and voiceovers in both Malay and English. These auditory features are vital for supporting different learning styles and preferences, particularly for young children who may be more inclined towards auditory learning (Gee, 2007). By engaging multiple senses, Figma software helped to create a more immersive learning experience that promotes vocabulary retention and language comprehension.

2.2 Leveraging Microsoft PowerPoint for Interface and Interaction

In tandem with Figma software, Microsoft PowerPoint was used to develop the user interface and overall layout of the VocaDual game. PowerPoint's straightforward and intuitive presentation tools provided an ideal platform for designing a visually appealing and easy-to-navigate framework (Altena et al., 2016). This choice allowed the development team to rapidly prototype various game elements, test them in real-time, and make quick adjustments based on user feedback.

PowerPoint's flexibility in creating hyperlinks and animations was especially valuable for incorporating interactive features such as clickable icons, moving objects, and transitions between different activities. These features contribute to an engaging user experience by allowing children to interact directly with the game content, fostering a sense of curiosity and exploration (Mayer, 2009).

The simplicity of the PowerPoint platform also meant that the game could be updated or adapted with ease, ensuring it remains relevant and effective as educational needs evolve.

2.3 Impact on the Game and the User Experience

The combination of Figma software and Microsoft PowerPoint significantly enhanced both the effectiveness of the game and the overall user experience. Figma's advanced design capabilities ensured that VocaDual was not only visually and audibly stimulating but also pedagogically sound, with interactive elements carefully designed to reinforce vocabulary retention through repetition and practice (Gagné et al., 2005). The software's ability to create a cohesive and engaging learning environment was key to developing a game that can sustain the interest of young children over time.

Meanwhile, PowerPoint's role in creating a user-friendly interface ensured that the game was easy to navigate, even for preschool students with limited digital literacy skills. The clear layout and consistent visual design helped to minimize cognitive load, allowing children to focus more on language learning activities rather than navigating the game itself (Sweller, 1988). The combination of these tools has also facilitated a smoother integration of VocaDual into classroom settings, as teachers can easily guide students through the game and tailor the experience to meet individual learning needs.

2.4 Overall Benefits of the Development Approach

By employing Figma software and Microsoft PowerPoint in the development of VocaDual, the creators have successfully crafted a bilingual learning tool that is not only effective but also engaging and accessible. The use of these tools has allowed for the creation of a game that combines playful, interactive activities with structured language instruction, making vocabulary acquisition in both Malay and English a fun and meaningful experience for preschool children.

This approach ensures that VocaDual can be easily adapted and updated based on ongoing feedback and changes in educational needs, making it a sustainable tool for bilingual education in Malaysia's diverse preschool settings. The successful use of these software tools in the development of VocaDual demonstrates the potential for technology to transform language learning, providing young learners with a strong foundation in bilingual skills that will benefit them throughout their educational journey (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The study on VocaDual, a bilingual vocabulary acquisition tool, was conducted using a qualitative observational approach at Tabika Perpaduan Taman Maju, Daerah Batu Pahat, Johor Darul Takzim. The aim was to assess the tool's effectiveness in enhancing language learning among preschool children. Participants included teachers and students aged 4 to 6 years, representing a typical preschool cohort in Malaysia where bilingual education is common.

Given the age of the students and their limited ability to articulate feedback through surveys, data collection focused on qualitative observations and interactions. Researchers conducted semi-structured interviews with teachers to explore their experiences with VocaDual, including how they integrated the tool into their teaching, its impact on students' language learning, and any challenges faced. Additionally, direct classroom observations were conducted to examine how the children interacted with VocaDual during activities. Researchers noted the children's engagement levels, enthusiasm, and language use while participating in interactive activities such as hidden animal games, jumble word games, and crossword puzzles.

Focus group sessions with students were also conducted in a playful manner, where researchers observed the children's spontaneous reactions, verbal expressions, and collaborative behaviors while using VocaDual. This approach allowed for an authentic understanding of how young learners engage with the tool in a real-world educational setting.

Thematic analysis was employed to identify key themes related to user engagement, learning outcomes, and potential integration challenges (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The primary material for the study was the VocaDual game itself, which features various interactive vocabulary-building activities designed to support bilingual education by enhancing vocabulary, spelling, and cognitive skills like problem-solving.

This real-life educational setting provided an in-depth perspective on the effectiveness of VocaDual and its applicability in daily teaching and learning contexts. The findings offer valuable insights into the tool's potential for broader application in multilingual educational settings, demonstrating its capacity to engage young learners and support bilingual vocabulary acquisition (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

4. FINDINGS

The study's findings on VocaDual demonstrate its effectiveness in enhancing bilingual vocabulary acquisition among preschool learners. Through a qualitative analysis of teacher interviews, student focus groups, and classroom observations, it was found that VocaDual significantly improved student engagement and motivation. Teachers reported that the interactive features, such as hidden animal games, jumble word puzzles, and crossword activities, captivated students' attention and fostered active learning, which contributed to better retention and use of new vocabulary in both English and their native language. Students showed notable progress in remembering and applying the vocabulary learned through these games in various contexts. However, the study also identified practical challenges, including the need for sufficient technological resources and adequate training for teachers to fully utilize the tool. Despite these challenges, the overall feedback was positive, suggesting that VocaDual could effectively complement traditional teaching methods and support bilingual education. The study concludes that VocaDual holds promise for wider application in multilingual educational environments, providing a dynamic and engaging solution to common language learning challenges faced by young learners in Malaysia.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings from the study suggest that VocaDual is a highly effective educational tool for enhancing bilingual vocabulary learning among young children in Malaysia. By incorporating interactive elements such as hidden animal games, jumble word puzzles, and crossword activities, VocaDual engages students more actively than traditional methods. These features encourage student participation and improve retention of vocabulary, making the learning process more engaging and dynamic.

Feedback from both teachers and students supports these observations, indicating that VocaDual positively impacts motivation and interest in language learning. Teachers have noted that the interactive nature of the game keeps students interested and motivated, leading to higher levels of engagement in language activities. Students find the game enjoyable and fun, which promotes a more positive attitude towards learning English and Malay vocabulary. This suggests that VocaDual not only supports language development but also fosters a love for learning, which is critical in early childhood education.

However, the discussion also highlights certain challenges that must be addressed to maximize the tool's effectiveness. One of the key issues is the need for adequate technological infrastructure in

educational settings. Schools must have access to devices and reliable internet connections to fully utilize VocaDual's features. Additionally, there is a need for teacher training to ensure that educators are comfortable and competent in using the tool in their classrooms. Teachers need to understand how to integrate VocaDual into their lesson plans effectively and how to use its features to enhance their teaching strategies.

6. CONCLUSION

VocaDual shows great promise as an innovative tool for enhancing bilingual vocabulary acquisition among young learners in Malaysia, effectively engaging students with interactive features such as hidden animal games, jumble word puzzles, and crossword activities that make language learning enjoyable and dynamic. The tool has demonstrated a positive impact on student participation, motivation, and vocabulary retention, as reported by both teachers and students. However, its successful implementation requires addressing challenges like the need for sufficient technological infrastructure and teacher training. While further research is needed to explore its long-term effectiveness and broader applications across various educational contexts and age groups, VocaDual represents a valuable advancement in language teaching, highlighting the importance of interactive, game-based learning to meet the diverse needs of learners and improve educational outcomes in multilingual settings.

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